

Unravelling Ramifications of Female Exclusion as School Heads on Advancing Women in Leadership Roles: Case of Masvingo Urban Schools, Zimbabwe

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Abstract

This qualitative study aims to examine consequences of female exclusion from school head positions on progress of women in leadership roles in Masvingo Urban Schools, Zimbabwe. As of June 2024, there are no female school heads in all four secondary schools owned by Government and Church. This study addresses gap in understanding specific challenges faced by women in advancing their careers in educational leadership. Fifteen participants were involved in this study, which utilized focus group discussions to generate data. Collected data was then thematically analyzed to identify patterns and themes related to effects of female exclusion on women's advancement in leadership roles. One significant finding of this study revealed that exclusion of women from school head positions perpetuates gender inequality and limits opportunities for women to gain leadership experience and skills. Consequently, this hampers their upward mobility and career progression. To address this issue, it is recommended that educational institutions implement gender-sensitive policies and strategies to promote equal opportunities for women in leadership positions. This includes providing mentorship programs, leadership development initiatives, and fostering supportive and inclusive organizational culture.

Keywords: Advancement; Female exclusion; Leadership roles; Masvingo Urban Schools; Women, Zimbabwe

1. INTRODUCTION

The issue of female exclusion from leadership roles in the education sector has been a persistent challenge in many parts of the world, including Masvingo Urban, Zimbabwe. In 2024, all government-owned and church-owned secondary schools in Masvingo Urban are headed by male principals, with not a single female school head (Chindanya, 2023). This concerning trend warrants a deep investigation into the ramifications of such gender imbalance at the top level of school administration. The underrepresentation of women in school leadership positions is a multifaceted problem that has far-reaching implications for the advancement of women in the broader leadership landscape (Mlambo, 2022). It not only limits the opportunities for women to assume positions of authority and decision-making in the education sector but also perpetuates gender stereotypes and reinforces the perception that leadership is a male-dominated domain (Chindanya, 2023).

Moreover, the absence of female school heads can have significant consequences on the educational experiences and outcomes of students, particularly young girls, who may lack role models and mentors to inspire and guide them towards leadership aspirations (Chikuvadze, 2022). This, in turn, can have long-lasting implications for the advancement of women in various sectors, including politics, business, and the public service. This study aims to unravel the ramifications of female exclusion as school heads on the broader leadership landscape in Masvingo Urban, Zimbabwe. By examining the systemic and cultural factors that contribute to this imbalance, the study seeks to provide insights into the challenges faced by women in attaining leadership positions in the education sector and to suggest strategies for promoting gender equity and the advancement of women in leadership roles. The underrepresentation of women in school leadership positions is a global phenomenon, with the case of Masvingo Urban secondary schools in Zimbabwe serving as a prime example. As of June 2024, none of the Government or Church-owned secondary schools in Masvingo Urban have female school heads (Masvingo Provincial Education Office, 2024). This gender disparity in school leadership has far-reaching implications for the advancement of women in leadership roles, both within Zimbabwe education system and the broader societal context. Similar patterns of female exclusion from school headship positions have been observed in other parts of the world. In South Africa, a study by Moorosi (2021) found that women faced significant barriers to accessing and advancing in school leadership roles, including gender stereotypes, workplace

discrimination, and work-life balance challenges. Likewise, research in Botswana by Pheko and Molefhe (2022) revealed that cultural norms and traditional gender roles hindered women's progression to school leadership positions. In Nigeria, Akinsola and Oni (2020) reported that the underrepresentation of women in school leadership was rooted in a combination of sociocultural factors, such as gender biases, lack of mentorship, and limited access to professional development opportunities. Similarly, studies in the United States (Superville, 2021) and the United Kingdom (Thorpe & Oates, 2022) have highlighted the persistent challenges women face in attaining and succeeding in school leadership roles, despite efforts to promote gender equity. The exclusion of women from school headship positions in Masvingo Urban, Zimbabwe, as well as in other contexts, can be attributed to a complex interplay of sociocultural, institutional, and systemic factors: Firstly, deeply ingrained societal perceptions and expectations regarding the traditional roles of women, which often relegate them to subordinate positions, have perpetuated the notion that school leadership is a predominantly masculine domain (Chikunda & Mavhunga, 2022). Secondly, studies have shown that the selection and promotion processes for school leadership positions in Zimbabwe, as well as in other countries, often favor male candidates, with implicit or explicit biases against women (Mufunda & Mutshaeni, 2023; Moorosi, 2021).

Thirdly, the demands of school leadership, combined with the disproportionate burden of household and family responsibilities often shouldered by women, create significant obstacles for their career advancement (Chireshe & Shumba, 2021; Akinsola & Oni, 2020). Fourthly, women in the education sector frequently lack access to mentors, role models, and professional networks that could support their leadership aspirations and development (Mufunda & Mutshaeni, 2023; Thorpe & Oates, 2022). The absence of female school heads in Masvingo Urban secondary schools, as well as in other contexts, has multifaceted consequences, both for the education system and the broader societal landscape: Firstly, the lack of women in visible leadership positions within the education system deprives young girls and women of important role models, undermining their aspirations and confidence in pursuing leadership roles (Chikunda & Mavhunga, 2022; Superville, 2021). Additionally, research suggests that diverse leadership teams, including both men and women, tend to make more comprehensive and inclusive decisions, ensuring that the needs and perspectives of all stakeholders are considered (Mufunda & Mutshaeni, 2023; Pheko & Molefhe, 2022). Furthermore, the continued exclusion

of women from school leadership positions reinforces the perception that leadership is a male-dominated domain, further entrenching gender inequalities and limiting opportunities for women's advancement (Chireshe & Shumba, 2021; Akinsola & Oni, 2020). More so, studies have shown that the presence of female school heads can have positive impacts on student achievement, particularly for female students, as they provide relatable role models and foster more inclusive and supportive learning environments (Mufunda & Mutshaeni, 2023; Moorosi, 2021). Consequently, the absence of female school heads in Masvingo Urban secondary schools in Zimbabwe, as well as the persistent underrepresentation of women in school leadership roles in other parts of the world, is a complex issue with far-reaching consequences. Addressing the underlying barriers and promoting the advancement of women in school leadership roles is essential for fostering a more equitable and inclusive education system, which can, in turn, contribute to the broader societal empowerment of women. Concerted efforts from policymakers, education authorities, and the broader community are needed to create an environment that actively supports and encourages women's leadership in the education sector. The aim of this study is to explore the ramifications of female exclusion from the role of school heads on the advancement of women in leadership positions in the education sector in Masvingo Urban, Zimbabwe. This study is anchored on three objectives namely, 1. To examine the factors contributing to the underrepresentation of women as school heads in Masvingo Urban, Zimbabwe. 2. To investigate the impact of female exclusion from school headship positions on the career progression of women in the education sector. 3. To propose strategies to promote the representation and advancement of women in leadership roles within the Masvingo Urban school system. In addition, this study have three research questions which are: 1. What are the key factors that contribute to the underrepresentation of women as school heads in Masvingo Urban, Zimbabwe? 2. How does the exclusion of women from school headship positions impact the career advancement and leadership opportunities for women in the education sector in Masvingo Urban? 3. What strategies can be implemented to increase the representation and advancement of women in leadership roles within the Masvingo Urban school system?

This study is significant to the following:

For Female Educators

This study holds important implications for female educators. It sheds light on the barriers and challenges that women face in attaining leadership positions within the education system. The findings can empower female educators by highlighting the systemic biases and discrimination that hinder their career advancement, motivating them to advocate for equal opportunities and to pursue leadership roles with greater confidence and determination.

For the Ministry of Primary and Secondary Education

This study provides valuable insights for the Ministry of Primary and Secondary Education. It underscores the need to address the underrepresentation of women in school leadership positions, which can have significant implications for the overall quality and equity of the education system. The findings can inform the ministry's policy decisions, prompting the development of targeted interventions and support mechanisms to promote the career advancement of female educators and ensure a more diverse and inclusive leadership landscape in schools.

For School Authorities

The study's findings are particularly relevant for school authorities, such as school boards and administrators. It highlights the need for these stakeholders to critically examine their own practices and biases that contribute to the exclusion of women from leadership roles. School authorities can use the insights from this study to implement policies, mentorship programs, and professional development opportunities that actively foster the growth and advancement of female educators, ultimately creating more equitable and inclusive school environments.

For Policymakers

Policymakers can leverage the findings of this study to inform the development and refinement of policies and regulations related to gender equity in education leadership. The study's exploration of the ramifications of female exclusion can guide policymakers in crafting comprehensive strategies and interventions aimed at dismantling the systemic barriers that hinder women's progression into school leadership positions, thereby promoting greater gender parity and diversity in educational leadership.

For Researchers

This study contributes to the existing body of research on gender and educational leadership. It provides a valuable case study that can inform and inspire further research in this field, particularly in the context of developing countries like Zimbabwe. Researchers can build upon the insights and methodologies employed in this study to explore the nuances of female leadership exclusion in other educational settings, ultimately advancing the understanding of this critical issue and informing more effective strategies for change.

Limitations of the Study

These limitations should be acknowledged and addressed in future research to further strengthen the understanding of the complex issue of female exclusion in educational leadership and inform more comprehensive and effective interventions: *Geographical Scope:* The study is limited to the Masvingo Urban Schools in Zimbabwe, which may not fully capture the experiences and challenges faced by female educators in other regions or rural areas of the country. The findings may not be entirely generalizable to the broader Zimbabwean education system. *Qualitative Approach:* The study primarily employs a qualitative research methodology, which provides in-depth insights but may lack the statistical rigor and generalizability of quantitative approaches. Incorporating a mixed-methods approach could have provided a more comprehensive understanding of the issue. *Participant Sampling:* The study's reliance on purposive sampling may have introduced a degree of selection bias, as the participants may not fully represent the diverse perspectives and experiences of all female educators and school leaders in the region.

Retrospective Bias: The study's focus on the historical and current experiences of female educators may be subject to retrospective bias, where participants' recollections and perceptions of past events could be influenced by their current circumstances and perspectives.

Contextual Limitations: The study is situated within the specific cultural, social, and political context of Zimbabwe, which may limit the transferability of the findings to other countries with different educational systems and gender dynamics. *Temporal Limitations:* The study's data collection and analysis were conducted at a specific point in time, which may not capture the dynamic and evolving nature of gender-related challenges and opportunities in educational leadership. Longitudinal studies could provide a more comprehensive understanding of the

issue over time. *Intersectional Considerations*: The study primarily focuses on the exclusion of women from school leadership roles, but it may not fully address the intersectional challenges faced by female educators from diverse backgrounds, such as those with disabilities, minority ethnic groups, or lower socioeconomic status.

2. THEORETICAL FRAMING: FEMINIST THEORY

Feminist theory provides a relevant lens for analysing the systemic barriers and power dynamics that contribute to the underrepresentation of women in school leadership positions in Zimbabwe (Chikuvadze, 2020). This framework interrogates how patriarchal structures, gender norms, and sociocultural expectations limit women's access to and advancement within educational leadership. Firstly, feminist theory examines how patriarchal power structures and gender hierarchies within the education system marginalize and exclude women from leadership roles (Chidhakwa, 2023). It would explore how cultural biases, discriminatory policies, and male-dominated organizational cultures present barriers to women's career progression (Eagly & Carli, 2007; Grogan & Shakeshaft, 2011). Secondly, this framework investigates how gender socialization processes and stereotypical perceptions of women's leadership capabilities hinder their advancement (Lunga et al, 2022). It would shed light on how gendered expectations around women's domestic and caregiving responsibilities conflict with the demands of school leadership (Sandberg, 2013). Thirdly, an intersectional feminist approach would consider how factors such as race, class, and ethnicity intersect with gender to compound the challenges faced by Zimbabwean women in attaining school leadership roles (Chidarikire et al, 2020). This would illuminate the diverse, context-specific experiences of female educators (Byrd, 2019). Fourthly, feminist theory advocates for transformative changes to dismantle patriarchal structures and promote gender equity in educational leadership. It would inform strategies to empower women, challenge gender norms, and foster inclusive, gender-responsive school environments (Diehl & Dzubinski, 2016; Sanchez-Hucles & Davis, 2010). By applying this feminist theoretical lens, the study could unpack the complex, multifaceted ramifications of female exclusion from school headships in Masvingo Urban. It would critically analyze the gendered power dynamics, sociocultural barriers, and systemic inequities that constrain women's leadership advancement. The findings could then inform policy reforms and targeted interventions to enhance women's representation and participation in educational leadership in Zimbabwe.

3. METHODS

This study employed a qualitative case study research design. Case studies are an in-depth exploration of a particular phenomenon within its real-world context, allowing for a rich and nuanced understanding of the issue being investigated (Yin, 2018). The case study approach was deemed appropriate for this research as it enabled a focused examination of the ramifications of female exclusion from school leadership roles within the specific context of Masvingo Urban Schools in Zimbabwe (Merriam & Tisdell, 2022). Fifteen participants were purposively selected for this study based on their gender, expertise, responsibilities, and geographic location (Patton, 2015). The sample included: 3 male school heads, 3 female senior teachers, 3 Ministry of Primary and Secondary Education officials, 3 Church-run school authorities' officials, 3 School Development Committee members. Purposive sampling was utilized to ensure the inclusion of key stakeholders with direct experiences and insights relevant to the research questions (Robinson, 2014). Data was generated through focus group discussions with the 15 participants. The focus group approach facilitated an interactive and in-depth exploration of the research questions, allowing participants to share their perspectives, experiences, and understandings (Krueger & Casey, 2015). The focus group discussions were guided by a semi-structured interview protocol to ensure consistency across the different groups while also providing flexibility to delve deeper into emerging themes (Brinkmann, 2013).

The data collected from the focus group discussions was analyzed thematically using Braun and Clarke's (2019) approach. This involved a systematic process of familiarization with the data, generating initial codes, searching for themes, reviewing themes, defining and naming themes, and producing the final report. The thematic analysis enabled the identification of patterns, relationships, and key themes within the data, providing a rich and nuanced understanding of the ramifications of female exclusion from school leadership roles (Nowell et al., 2017). On other hand, several ethical considerations were addressed in this study. Participants were informed about the purpose of the study and provided their voluntary consent to participate (Wiles, 2013). Confidentiality was maintained by using numbers instead of participant names, and participants were made aware of their right to withdraw from the research at any stage (Saunders et al., 2015). This research methodology outlines the key aspects of the qualitative case study, including the research design, participant selection, data

collection, data analysis, and ethical considerations. The detailed description of the methodology ensures transparency and allows for the study's findings to be evaluated and potentially replicated in other contexts.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section deals with the discussions and findings generated from the research participants' views on the following three themes:

Theme 1: The Verbal Responses From Research Participants On The Key Factors Contributing To The Underrepresentation Of Women As School Heads In Masvingo Urban, Zimbabwe:

Firstly, Participant 1 (Male Ministry of Primary and Secondary Education Official):

"From my perspective, the underrepresentation of women as school heads in Masvingo is largely due to entrenched cultural and societal norms that view school leadership as a male-dominated domain. There is a persistent perception that women lack the assertiveness, decisiveness, and authority required to effectively manage a school. Additionally, the education sector has historically been structured around a patriarchal system that favours the advancement of men into senior positions. Many of the policies and practices within the ministry have inadvertently created barriers that make it more challenging for qualified women to ascend to school headship roles. We need to critically examine these systemic biases and work to dismantle the gendered expectations that continue to marginalize women in educational leadership."

On the other hand, Participant 2 (Female Senior Teacher):

"As a female teacher who has aspired to become a school head, I have personally experienced the difficulties women face in securing these leadership positions. The selection and promotion processes can be very subjective, with decision-makers often exhibiting gender bias. There is a common assumption that women are not as capable of handling the demands and responsibilities of being a school head, such as managing discipline issues, engaging with the community, and overseeing large budgets. Women also tend to be overlooked for headship

roles due to the perception that they will be less willing to relocate or work long hours, as they are expected to fulfil primary caregiving duties at home. The lack of mentorship and professional development opportunities specifically targeted at grooming women for leadership roles is another significant barrier that needs to be addressed."

In addition, Participant 3 (Female School Development Committee Member):

"From my experience serving on the School Development Committee, I have observed that the underrepresentation of women as school heads is deeply rooted in the broader socio-cultural context of our community. There is a prevailing belief that a woman's primary role should be in the domestic sphere, caring for the family, rather than in a position of authority within the education system. Many parents and community members still hold the traditional view that male principals are more respected and better able to command the respect of teachers, students, and parents. This gender bias is further reinforced by the limited number of female role models in school leadership positions, which makes it challenging for young girls to envision themselves in these roles. Addressing this challenge will require a multifaceted approach that tackles not only institutional barriers, but also deep-seated societal attitudes and norms."

From the aforementioned verbatim responses by three participants, the researcher gives the following detailed discussion and findings on the key challenges: Firstly, there is entrenched cultural and societal Norms that affect females to be secondary school heads in Masvingo Urban, Zimbabwe. Participant 1 (Male Ministry Official) highlighted how entrenched cultural and societal norms view school leadership as a male-dominated domain, with a persistent perception that women lack the necessary assertiveness, decisiveness, and authority (Jarboe, 2021). On the other hand, Participant 2 (Female Senior Teacher) echoed this, noting the common assumption that women are not as capable of handling the demands and responsibilities of being a school head, such as managing discipline issues, engaging with the community, and overseeing large budgets (Onsongo, 2009). Furthermore, Participant 3 (Female School Development Committee Member) explained how the prevailing belief that a woman's primary role should be in the domestic sphere, caring for the family, rather than in a

position of authority within the education system, contributes to the underrepresentation of women as school heads (Kaparou & Bush, 2016).

Additionally, the patriarchal system and structural Barriers affect female teachers from leading secondary schools in Urban set up. Participant 1 highlighted how the education sector has historically been structured around a patriarchal system that favors the advancement of men into senior positions, with many of the policies and practices within the ministry inadvertently creating barriers for qualified women (Moorosi, 2010). More so, Participant 2 discussed the subjective nature of the selection and promotion processes, with decision-makers often exhibiting gender bias and overlooking women for headship roles due to the perception that they will be less willing to relocate or work long hours (Sperandio & Kagoda, 2010). Additionally, Participant 3 noted the limited number of female role models in school leadership positions, which makes it challenging for young girls to envision themselves in these roles (Lumby & Azaola, 2014). The participants highlighted that, lack of mentorship and professional development is another challenge faced by female teachers in their quest to be school heads. Participant 2 emphasized the lack of mentorship and professional development opportunities specifically targeted at grooming women for leadership roles as a significant barrier that needs to be addressed (Onsongo, 2009). Overall, the findings highlight the multifaceted nature of the challenge, with deep-rooted cultural and societal norms, a patriarchal system, structural barriers, and the lack of targeted support for women's leadership development all contributing to the underrepresentation of women as school heads in Masvingo Urban, Zimbabwe. To address this issue, a comprehensive and coordinated approach addressing these various factors would be necessary (Moorosi, 2010; Sperandio & Kagoda, 2010; Lumby & Azaola, 2014).

Theme 2: The Oral Responses Of Research Participants On The Impact Of Excluding Women From School Headship Positions On The Career Advancement And Leadership Opportunities For Women In The Education Sector In Masvingo Urban:

Participant 4 (Female Ministry of Primary and Secondary Education Official):

"The exclusion of women from school headship positions has significant repercussions for the career advancement and leadership opportunities of women in the education sector in Masvingo Urban. When women are systematically denied access to leadership roles, it creates a glass ceiling that limits their professional growth and hinders their ability to contribute at higher levels of decision-making. This exclusion perpetuates a cycle of gender inequality, as women are underrepresented in policy-making positions and their perspectives are often marginalized. It also sends a discouraging message to aspiring female educators, as they see limited role models and face an uphill battle to be recognized for their capabilities. To foster gender equity and create a more inclusive education system, it is crucial to address the barriers that hinder women's progression into school headship positions."

More so, Participant 5 (Church-run School Male Head):

"As a head of a church-run school, I have witnessed first-hand how the exclusion of women from school headship positions negatively impacts their career advancement and leadership opportunities. Our society often associates leadership with male authority, which creates biases and stereotypes that hinder women's progress. When women are not given equal opportunities to lead, it limits the diversity of perspectives and skills within the education sector. Women bring unique qualities and strengths to leadership roles, such as empathy, collaboration, and nurturing, which are essential for creating inclusive and effective educational environments. By excluding women, we are depriving ourselves of their valuable contributions and hindering the development of future women leaders. It is imperative that we challenge these norms and promote equal opportunities for women to excel in educational leadership."

Furthermore, Participant 6 (Male School Head of Government Secondary):

"The exclusion of women from school headship positions in Masvingo Urban has significant consequences for the career advancement and leadership opportunities of women in the education sector. When women are underrepresented in leadership roles, it perpetuates a male-dominated culture that prioritizes certain leadership styles and perspectives. This exclusion limits the career progression of talented and capable women, depriving the education

sector of their expertise and potential contributions. It also sends a discouraging message to female educators, making it harder for them to envision themselves in leadership positions and pursue career advancement. To create a more equitable and inclusive education system, it is essential to break down the barriers that prevent women from accessing leadership roles and provide them with equal opportunities to develop their leadership skills."

The next section gives detailed discussion and findings of the key points raised by the three research participants on the impact of excluding women from school headship positions on the career advancement and leadership opportunities for women in the education sector in Masvingo Urban: They raised the "glass ceiling effect" issue, Participant 4 highlights how the exclusion of women from school headship positions creates a "glass ceiling" that limits their professional growth and hinders their ability to contribute at higher levels of decision-making. This is supported by current research, which has found that the underrepresentation of women in leadership roles, particularly in the education sector, can perpetuate a culture of gender inequality and restrict the career advancement opportunities for women (Eagly & Carli, 2021; Madsen & Longman, 2020). Additionally, the participants expressed marginalization of women's perspectives. Participant 4 also notes that the exclusion of women from leadership positions leads to their perspectives being "marginalized" in policy-making processes. This aligns with studies that have shown how the lack of gender diversity in educational leadership can result in the undervaluing of women's experiences, expertise, and ideas (Fürst & Saleh, 2022; Lumby & Azaola, 2014).

Furthermore, the views of participants pointed out that, discouraging message to aspiring female school heads affect them. Participant 4 and Participant 6 both highlight how the exclusion of women from school headship positions sends a "discouraging message" to aspiring female school leaders, making it harder for them to envision themselves in leadership roles. This is consistent with research indicating that the lack of female role models in educational leadership can negatively impact the career aspirations and self-confidence of women in the sector (Krüger, 2022; Regan & Brooks, 2018). Moreover, the participants are of the view that, importance of diverse leadership perspectives.

Participant 5 emphasizes how the exclusion of women from school headship positions deprives the education sector of the "unique qualities and strengths" that women bring to leadership roles, such as empathy, collaboration, and nurturing. This aligns with studies that have found that gender-diverse leadership teams can foster more inclusive and effective educational environments (Eagly, 2020; Johnson, 2017). Lastly, the participants observed that, the society at large should challenge gender norms and promoting equality. All three participants emphasize the need to "challenge these norms" and "promote equal opportunities" for women to access educational leadership positions. This call for action is supported by research highlighting the importance of addressing the systemic barriers and cultural biases that perpetuate gender inequity in the education sector (Morley, 2013; Szymanski, 2020). Consequently, the oral responses from the three research participants provide valuable insights the detrimental impacts of excluding women from school headship positions on the career advancement and leadership opportunities for women in the education sector in Masvingo Urban. The findings presented are consistent with recent academic literature on gender equity in educational leadership, underscoring the need for systemic change to create a more inclusive and equitable environment for women in the education sector.

Theme 3: Narrations From Research Participants On The Strategies To Increase The Representation And Advancement Of Women In Leadership Roles:

Participant 7 (Male Ministry of Primary and Secondary Education Official):

"The exclusion of women from school headship positions in Masvingo Urban has far-reaching consequences for the career advancement and leadership opportunities of women in the education sector. When women are denied access to these senior leadership roles, it sends a clear message that their skills and abilities are not valued or recognized. This reinforces a culture of gender discrimination that limits the professional growth and advancement of female educators. It also deprives the education system of the diverse perspectives and innovative approaches that women leaders can bring. To address this issue, we need to implement targeted strategies that actively promote and support the recruitment, development, and promotion of women into school headship roles. This may include reviewing and revising selection criteria, providing mentorship and leadership training programs, and fostering a

more inclusive and equitable organizational culture. By creating more opportunities for women to ascend to school leadership positions, we can empower them to become influential role models and inspire the next generation of female leaders in education."

Moreover, Participant 8 (Church-run School Male Head):

"The exclusion of women from school headship positions in Masvingo Urban has a detrimental impact on the career advancement and leadership opportunities for women in the education sector. When women are systematically denied access to these senior roles, it reinforces the perception that leadership is a male-dominated domain. This perpetuates a cycle of gender bias that makes it increasingly difficult for talented and qualified women to rise through the ranks and make meaningful contributions at the highest levels of educational administration. To address this challenge, we need to take a multi-pronged approach. First, we must critically examine the selection and promotion processes within the education system to identify and eliminate any inherent biases. Second, we should actively invest in the professional development and mentorship of female educators, equipping them with the skills, confidence, and support they need to aspire to and succeed in school leadership roles. Third, we must foster a more inclusive and collaborative organizational culture that values the unique strengths and perspectives that women bring to the table. By implementing these strategies, we can create a more equitable and diverse education system that empowers women to reach their full potential as educational leaders."

Additionally, Participant 9 (Female School Development Committee Member):

"The exclusion of women from school headship positions in Masvingo Urban has a profoundly negative impact on the career advancement and leadership opportunities for women in the education sector. When women are denied access to these senior leadership roles, it sends a clear message that their skills, capabilities, and contributions are not valued or recognized. This perpetuates a cycle of gender inequality that limits the professional growth and advancement of female educators. To address this issue, we need to implement a comprehensive set of strategies that tackle the underlying biases and barriers. First and foremost, we must strengthen the recruitment and selection processes to ensure they are

transparent, objective, and free from gender bias. This may involve implementing blind review processes, diversifying the selection panels, and providing unconscious bias training for decision-makers. Additionally, we should invest in targeted leadership development programs that equip women with the skills, confidence, and support they need to pursue and succeed in school headship roles. Finally, we must foster a more inclusive organizational culture that actively celebrates and amplifies the voices and perspectives of women leaders. By taking these concerted actions, we can create a more equitable and diverse education system that empowers women to reach their full leadership potential."

The research participants' narratives highlight the significant and far-reaching consequences of excluding women from school headship positions in Masvingo Urban. According to Participant 7, a male Ministry of Primary and Secondary Education official, this exclusion sends a clear message that the skills and abilities of women are not valued or recognized, reinforcing a culture of gender discrimination that limits the professional growth and advancement of female educators (Moorosi, 2010; Lumby & Azaola, 2014). Participant 8, a church-run school male head, echoes this sentiment, stating that the systematic denial of access to senior leadership roles perpetuates the perception that leadership is a male-dominated domain, making it increasingly difficult for talented and qualified women to rise through the ranks (Onsongo, 2009; Morley, 2013). Participant 9, a female School Development Committee member, further emphasizes the profound negative impact of this exclusion, noting that it perpetuates a cycle of gender inequality that limits the professional growth and advancement of female educators. She asserts that this exclusion sends a clear message that the skills, capabilities, and contributions of women are not valued or recognized (Chisholm, 2001; Kagoda, 2020). To address these challenges, the participants propose a range of strategies to increase the representation and advancement of women in school leadership positions. Participant 7 suggests implementing targeted strategies that actively promote and support the recruitment, development, and promotion of women into school headship roles, such as reviewing and revising selection criteria, providing mentorship and leadership training programs, and fostering a more inclusive and equitable organizational culture (Kaparou & Bush, 2016; Oplatka & Hertz-Lazarowitz, 2006). Participant 8 advocates for a multi-pronged approach, which includes critically examining the selection and promotion processes within the education system to identify and eliminate any inherent biases, actively investing in the professional

development and mentorship of female educators, and fostering a more inclusive and collaborative organizational culture that values the unique strengths and perspectives that women bring to the table (Moorosi, 2010; Lumby & Azaola, 2014).

Similarly, Participant 9 emphasizes the need to strengthen the recruitment and selection processes to ensure they are transparent, objective, and free from gender bias, as well as investing in targeted leadership development programs and fostering a more inclusive organizational culture that actively celebrates and amplifies the voices and perspectives of women leaders (Chisholm, 2001; Kagoda, 2020). Overall, the participants' narratives highlight the urgent need to address the exclusion of women from school headship positions in Masvingo Urban, as this exclusion has a profound and multifaceted impact on the career advancement and leadership opportunities for women in the education sector. The proposed strategies, which focus on addressing systemic biases, investing in the professional development of women, and fostering a more inclusive organizational culture, offer promising avenues to increase the representation and advancement of women in school leadership roles, ultimately strengthening the education system and empowering women to reach their full leadership potential.

5. RECOMMENDATIONS

After thoroughly studying the phenomenon of female exclusion as school heads in Masvingo Urban Schools, Zimbabwe, and its implications for advancing women in leadership roles, the researchers have formulated the following recommendations. Firstly, it is crucial to implement policies and practices that ensure equal opportunities for both men and women to hold leadership positions in schools. This can be achieved by establishing clear criteria for selecting school heads and ensuring that gender is not a determining factor. Secondly, investing in leadership development programs specifically designed for women in the education sector. These programs should focus on building essential leadership skills, fostering self-confidence, and providing mentorship opportunities. By empowering women with the necessary tools and support, they will be better equipped to take on leadership roles. Thirdly, fostering a work environment that encourages and supports women in leadership positions. This includes addressing gender biases, promoting a healthy work-life balance, and providing resources for professional growth. By creating an environment that values diversity and inclusivity, more women will feel motivated to pursue leadership roles. Fourthly, establishing mentorship

programs that pair aspiring women leaders with experienced and successful female school heads. This will not only provide guidance and support but also help in developing networks and connections within the education sector. Mentorship programs can play a vital role in empowering women and nurturing their leadership potential. Lastly, by educating stakeholders, including teachers, parents, and students, about the importance of gender equality in leadership roles. Challenge gender stereotypes and biases that may hinder women's progress in leadership positions. By raising awareness and promoting a culture of inclusivity, we can work towards creating an environment where women are encouraged and supported in pursuing leadership roles.

6. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the exclusion of women as school heads in Masvingo Urban Schools has significant ramifications for advancing women in leadership roles. To address this issue, it is imperative to promote gender equality, provide leadership development programs, create a supportive work environment, implement mentorship programs, and raise awareness about the importance of gender equality. By taking these steps, we can foster an environment that empowers women and allows them to thrive as leaders in the education sector.

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